

An SDP Relaxation in the Complex Domain for the Efficient Coordination of BESS and DGs in Single-Phase Distribution Grids while Considering Reactive Power Capabilities

Víctor M. Garrido-Arévalo^a, Oscar Danilo Montoya^{b,*}, Walter Gil-González^c, Luis Fernando Grisales-Noreña^d, Jesus C. Hernández^e

^aPrograma de Ingeniería Eléctrica, Facultad de Ingenierías y Arquitectura, Universidad de Pamplona, Pamplona 760042, Colombia.

^bGrupo de Compatibilidad e Interferencia Electromagnética, Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas, Bogotá 110231, Colombia.

^cDepartment of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Universidad Tecnológica de Pereira, Pereira 660003, Colombia.

^dDepartment of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Universidad de Talca, Curicó 3340000, Chile.

^eDepartment of Electrical Engineering, Campus Lagunillas s/n, University of Jaén, Edificio A3, 23071 Jaén, Spain

Abstract

This research proposes an efficient design of an energy management system for medium-voltage distribution networks from a perspective of convex optimization. The exact nonlinear programming problem that represents the functioning of distributed energy resources (DERs), such as batteries and photovoltaic sources, is approximated as an equivalent semi-definite programming (SDP) problem. This SDP approximation is achieved in the complex domain using Hermitian matrices, which are the equivalent of positive semi-definite matrices in the real number domain. Two test feeders, one with 27 nodes and the other with 33 nodes, are modified to match the characteristics of Colombian rural and urban networks. The 27-bus grid is adapted to accommodate the demand for and conditions of solar generation in the municipality of Capurganá, while the average demand and solar generation profiles of the city of Medellín are used for the 33-bus grid. One of the main contributions of this research is that it considers a DER operation with variable power factors, which allows for significant improvements compared to the traditional use of a unitary power factor scheme. Numerical comparisons are conducted using metaheuristic optimizers, including parallel versions of the particle swarm optimizer, the vortex search algorithm, and the continuous version of the genetic algorithm. These comparisons demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed SDP approximation. All simulations are carried out in the MATLAB software (version 2022b), using the disciplined convex optimizer (CVX) and the SDPT3 and SEDUMI solvers.

Keywords: Semi-definite approximation in the complex domain; Hermitian semidefinite matrices; Distributed energy resources; Battery energy storage systems; Photovoltaic generation; Variable power factor operation.

Nomenclature

Parameters

Δ_h	Fraction of time associated with the measuring process of the electrical variables (h).
$\Upsilon_{k,m}$	Admittance value associated with the physical connection between k and m nodes (S).
$\Upsilon_{n,n}$	Nodal admittance matrix in the complex domain (S).
\mathbb{Z}_{km}	Impedance value associated with the branch that connects nodes k and m (Ω).
φ_k^b	Battery charge/discharge coefficient (%/Wh).
$C_{AOM,k}^n$	Average administration, operation, and maintenance costs of the BESS connected at bus k (USD\$/Wh).

$C_{AOM,k}^{dg}$	Average administration, operation, and maintenance costs of the DG connected at bus k (USD\$/Wh).
$C_{kWh,k}^g$	Average energy purchasing costs in terminals of the substation (USD\$/Wh).
$G_{k,h}^{dg}$	Daily availability generation curve associated with the dispersed source connected at bus k (%)
h_{\min}	First element in the set of periods.
h_{\max}	Last element in the set of periods.
$P_{k,\max}^b$	Upper active power bound for a battery type- b connected at bus k (W).
$P_{k,\min}^b$	Lower active power bound for a battery type- b connected at bus k (W).
$S_{k,nom}^b$	Maximum apparent power transference capabilities in the battery type- b connected at bus k (VA).
$S_{k,nom}^{dg}$	Maximum apparent power generation capabilities in the dispersed generator connected at bus k (VA).

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: victor.garrido@unipamplona.edu.co (Víctor M. Garrido-Arévalo), odmontoyag@udistrital.edu.co (Oscar Danilo Montoya), wjgil@utp.edu.co (Walter Gil-González), luis.grisales@utalca.cl (Luis Fernando Grisales-Noreña), jcasa@ujaen.es (Jesus C. Hernández)

$S_{k,\text{nom}}^g$ Maximum apparent power generation capabilities in the conventional source connected at bus k (VA).

$SoC_{k,f}^b$ Final state-of-charge in battery type- b connected at bus k (%).

$SoC_{k,i}^b$ Initial state-of-charge in battery type- b connected at bus k (%).

V_{max} Upper voltage regulation bound (V).

V_{min} Lower voltage regulation bound (V).

$I_{km,\text{max}}$ Maximum current transference capability associated with the conductor that connects nodes k and m (A).

Sets

H Set containing all the periods.

L Set containing all the network branches.

N Set containing all the network nodes.

Variables

$\mathbb{I}_{km,h}$ Complex current flow in the branch that connects nodes k and m (A).

$S_{k,h}^g$ Complex power generation in terminals of the generator connected at bus k in time h (VA).

$S_{k,h}^b$ Complex power generation/consumption in a BESS connected to the k in time h (VA).

$S_{k,h}^{dg}$ Complex power generation in a DG connected to the k in time h (VA).

$S_{k,h}^d$ Complex power consumption at node k in period h (W).

$\mathbb{V}_{k,h}$ Complex voltage value at bus k in period h (V).

$\mathbb{V}_{m,h}$ Complex voltage value at bus m in period h (V).

$\mathbb{X}_{n,n,h}$ Complex square matrix with dimensions $n \times n$ defining one for each time h (V^2),

E_{costs} The expected value of the network operative costs (USD\$/day).

E_{loss} The expected value of the daily energy loss value (Wh/day).

$SoC_{k,h+1}^b$ State-of-charge in battery type- b connected at bus k in time $h + 1$ (%).

$SoC_{k,h}^b$ State-of-charge in battery type- b connected at bus k in time h (%).

$J_{km,h}$ Square value of the current flowing in the route that connects k and m nodes in period h (A^2)

1. Introduction

1.1. General context

Transitioning from fossil fuel-dominated electrical networks to sustainable grids is an essential contribution to the decarbonization of the electricity sector [1, 2]. One of the main ways to reduce the use of fossil fuels in electricity generation is to use renewable generation systems, thus supplying energy users with non-polluting energy [3, 4]. These systems are mostly based on photovoltaic (PV) or wind technologies, as they are the most mature. However, one of the main weaknesses of renewable generation technologies is the non-predictable nature of their primary resource, *e.g.*, solar irradiance or wind speed, which exhibit a stochastic behavior. This implies the need for the joint use of reliable energy storage systems in order to exploit their full potential [5, 6]. In the electricity market, energy storage systems are regarded as the ideal complement for renewable energy sources; combining them allows taking advantage of the renewable energy surplus when the electrical demand is low, storing this energy to later supply it to the grid when energy availability decreases and the electrical demand increases [7, 8].

Medium-voltage distribution grids constitute a particular scenario regarding the massive integration of renewable energy resources and energy storage systems, as they are the physical interface between large-scale transmission systems, sub-transmission systems, and end-users [9]. The main advantage of integrating these technologies, also known as *distributed energy resources* (DERs), is the electrical proximity between energy production and consumers, which improves quality, reliability, safety, and efficiency indices with regard to energy distribution and commercialization activities [10]. However, the use of DERs has caused distribution networks to transition from classical passive systems with unidirectional power flows to active distribution grids with bidirectional and time-coupling power flows [11]. This constitutes a new operation paradigm with regard to planning, operating, and controlling medium-voltage distribution networks, which requires developing new methodologies for an efficient operation and coordination of DERs while considering time coupling between renewable energy resources, energy storage systems' operation states, and the electricity demand of a given period of operation [12].

1.2. Motivation

Considering the importance of massive DERs integration in electrical networks and its positive effects from technical, economic, and environmental viewpoints [], this research aims to define an efficient energy management system (EMS) for medium-voltage distribution networks with a high penetration of renewable energy resources and batteries. Recently, the authors of [13] proposed an EMS for distribution grids that considers PV generation and batteries and solves the exact nonlinear programming (NLP) model representing the EMS through metaheuristic optimizers. Even though, given their ease of implementation [14], using metaheuristic algorithms is a typical solution methodology to analyze electrical networks

in day-ahead economic scenarios and optimal power flow studies, they cannot ensure a global optimum and may yield different solutions in every execution, *i.e.*, they are not fully reliable [15].

Given the high likelihood of obtaining local optima with metaheuristic algorithms [16], this research proposes an efficient EMS that employs convex optimization. Convex optimization is an excellent alternative for operating electrical networks, which is due to the properties of convex objective functions and solution spaces. Moreover, it allows finding global optima, with the main advantage that the solution is 100% reliable and repeatable with the same input parameter set.

1.3. Literature review

Several approaches have been suggested in the specialized literature to tackle the efficient coordination of BESS and DERs in single-phase AC distribution grids [6]. These approaches primarily focus on DERs, specifically those that utilize solar energy, with the objective of enhancing different financial, technical, and environmental aspects [17]. They also integrate BESS to manage the uncertainty of DERs, and they use fluctuations in power demand and electricity costs to operate properly. Furthermore, while managing the energy from DERs, these approaches ensure the proper operation of all elements in the network, meeting all its technical and operational requirements [18]. These requirements include generator power constraints, battery state of charge and charge/discharge power limits, maximum power transfer through distribution lines, and nodal voltage bounds [19]. Some of these approaches are described below.

The study by [20] introduced a mathematical model to optimize the mixed operation of PV systems and BESS. It formulated a mixed-integer linear programming model to manage the integrated PV-BESS system and solved it using the GAMS solver. The primary aim of this work was to reduce network operating costs. Numerical results in several scenarios showed the satisfactory performance of the proposed model, considering the time it took GAMS to solve the model. Nevertheless, this study did not employ comparison methodologies to showcase the model's robustness.

The work by [21] addressed the challenge of managing and setting up energy storage systems within electrical AC grids by employing a convex optimization approach that involved CVXGEN. The primary aim of their work was to reduce the energy costs associated with the operation and configuration of BESS. To showcase the efficacy of the proposed methodology, a comparative analysis against alternative solution approaches documented in the literature was conducted, including the SDPT3 solver. Furthermore, this work evaluated the time needed for the method to reach a solution while also emphasizing its satisfactory performance in terms of solution quality.

The authors of [22] implemented a model based on second-order cone programming (SOCP) to optimize the operation of energy storage systems within AC distribution grids. Their primary goal was to reduce the costs related to energy losses and greenhouse gas emissions over one

day of operation. This study employed CVX in the MATLAB/software to solve the model, as well as several simulation scenarios to showcase its performance. However, it did not include a comparative analysis of their results with other works.

The study by [23] applied SOCP and semi-definite programming (SDP) formulations to manage energy storage systems within three-phase distribution networks while aiming for the minimization of power losses and energy purchasing costs. The SOCP formulation was implemented in GAMS, and the SDP one was evaluated in YALMIP using the Mosek solver.

The authors of [24] developed a non-linear programming model for the intelligent operation of energy storage systems, which was solved using GAMS. The primary objective of this study was to minimize greenhouse gas emissions and energy losses during a single day of operation in test systems with 33 and 69 nodes, which represented urban networks. While the numerical results affirmed the effectiveness of the proposed methodology, no comparisons with other methods were made.

In addition, many approaches have been recently proposed to efficiently coordinate DERs in single-phase AC distribution grids. These approaches are based on intelligent algorithms such as the gravitational search algorithm [25], the genetic algorithm [26], the Chu & Beasley genetic algorithm [27], the non-sorting genetic algorithm [28], the coyote optimization algorithm [?], and the parallel version of the particle swarm optimizer (PSO) [29], among others. Although these approaches yield good results, none of them can ensure a global optimum or solution repeatability. This means that a satisfactory solution can only be provided in some cases.

Unlike the above-presented approaches, this paper presents a solution to the issue of efficiently coordinating BESS and DERs in single-phase AC distribution grids. This solution is achieved via a SDP model, which ensures the global optimum of the problem. Additionally, it converts the solution space from \mathcal{R}^n to $\mathcal{R}^{n \times n}$, which may seem counter-intuitive at first but provides improved geometrical properties.

1.4. Contributions and scope

In light of the above, these are the main contributions of this research:

- i. The formulation of an EMS for the efficient operation of DERs in distribution networks via NLP theory in the complex domain, as well as its transformation into a convex optimization equivalent using SDP theory while considering Hermitian matrices.
- ii. The inclusion of the reactive power capabilities of power electronic converters interfacing batteries and renewable energy sources based on PV technology to maximize the benefits of a daily operation when considering technical and economic objective functions.

In the scope of this research, it is assumed that: (i) the location and size of the DERs have been previously defined by the distribution system operator, which implies that

this research focuses on designing an efficient EMS while considering these locations and sizes as fixed inputs; (ii) the demand and renewable generation curves correspond to average values from historical data in the distribution networks' area of influence (these data are regarded as constant inputs the proposed EMS via convex optimization); and (iii) the dynamic active and reactive power control capabilities of the DERs are included via the power electronic converters that interface them with the grids, which implies that this research tests a scenario involving a variable power factor operation of the renewable generators and batteries. In the current literature, the typical operation of DERs considers a unitary power factor.

1.5. Document structure

This document is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the general formulation of the EMS for the efficient operation of DERs in medium-voltage distribution grids, by means of an NLP formulation in complex-domain variables. Section 3 describes the convexification of the NLP model via SDP theory in the complex domain via Hermitian semi-definite matrices. Section 4 presents the test systems used and their main characteristics, while Section 5 shows the the computational validation of the proposed model, as well as a comparison against intelligent algorithms. Finally, Section 6 lists the main conclusions of this work, in addition to proposals for future work.

2. Exact problem formulation

Designing an effective EMS for coordinating BESS and DERs in medium-voltage distribution grids while considering a day-ahead scenario requires solving an NLP model belonging to the family of non-convex optimization problems. Different performance indicators can be considered in the analysis to deal with the efficient coordination of these distributed energy resources, including technical, economic, or environmental indexes. This research considers a technical indicator corresponding to the daily energy losses and a financial objective function regarding the expected energy purchasing costs, including the operating expenses of BESS and DGs. Each of these objective functions is presented below.

2.1. Power losses minimization

One of the most classical objective functions implemented in power and distribution systems studies is the minimization of the expected power or energy losses associated with transforming electrical energy into heat in the resistive components of the distribution conductors. The general daily energy loss calculation in distribution grids using the complex variable domain representation is defined in Equation (1).

$$\min E_{\text{loss}} = \text{Re} \left\{ \sum_{h \in \mathbf{H}} \sum_{k \in \mathbf{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathbf{N}} \mathbb{Y}_{k,m} \mathbb{V}_{k,h}^* \mathbb{V}_{m,h} \Delta_h \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where E_{loss} represents the daily energy loss value, $\mathbb{V}_{k,h}$ and $\mathbb{V}_{m,h}$ are the representation of the voltage variables in the complex

domain for nodes k and m at time h ; $\mathbb{Y}_{k,m}$ is the km^{th} position of the nodal admittance matrix $\mathbb{Y}_{n,n}$. Δ_h represents the data length regarding daily operation analysis, typically one hour or less (i.e., 15 min, 30 min, or another fraction). Observe that \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{N} represent sets containing all the periods of analysis and the network nodes, respectively.

Remark 1. *The objective function in (1) exhibits a nonlinear structure associated with the product among complex voltages; however, it is a quadratic function that belongs to the family of convex functions owing to the nodal admittance matrix is a hermitian positive semidefinite matrix [30].*

2.2. Operative costs minimization

From the point of view of the utility companies, the main objective in the operation of DERs in their networks corresponds to the maximization of the electricity distribution profit, which is directly associated with the reduction of the total grid operative costs. In this sense, an essential objective function that must be considered can be the minimization of the expected daily operative costs, i.e., E_{cost} , which corresponds to the summation of the energy purchasing costs in terminals of the substation, and the operation and maintenance costs of the BESS and DGs. This objective function is presented in (2).

$$\min E_{\text{cost}} = \text{Re} \left\{ \sum_{k \in \mathbf{N}} \sum_{h \in \mathbf{H}} (C_{\text{kWh},k}^g \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^g + C_{\text{AOM},k}^{dg} \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{dg}) \Delta_h \right\} + \sum_{k \in \mathbf{N}} \sum_{h \in \mathbf{H}} C_{\text{kWh},k}^b \left| \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^b \right\} \right| \Delta_h, \quad (2)$$

where $C_{\text{kWh},k}^g$ corresponds to the expected energy purchasing costs in terminals of the substation, $C_{\text{AOM},k}^{dg}$ and $C_{\text{AOM},k}^b$ are the daily administration, maintenance, and operating costs associated with the energy production in the DG or BESS connected at bus k ; $\mathbb{S}_{k,h}^g$ is the complex power generation in terminals of the generator connected at bus k in time h , $\mathbb{S}_{k,h}^b$ is the complex power generation/consumption in a BESS connected to the k in time h , and $\mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{dg}$ corresponds the complex power generation of the DG connected at bus k in period h .

Remark 2. *The objective function defined in (2) represents the expected daily operative costs of the distribution networks, i.e., is an economic performance indicator with an essential characteristic that is convex since it is composed of a summation of linear and absolute value functions [31].*

2.3. Set of constraints

The problem of the efficient operation of DERs in distribution networks requires satisfying a set of multiple constraints associated with Kirchhoff's laws applied to each network node per period and also with the device's capacities. The EMS for the optimal coordination of DERs in medium voltage distribution networks has the set of constraints defined from (3) to (15).

$$\mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{g,\star} + \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{dg,\star} + \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{b,\star} - \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{d,\star} = \mathbb{V}_{k,h}^{\star} \sum_{m \in \mathbf{N}} \mathbb{Y}_{k,m} \mathbb{V}_{m,h}, \quad \begin{cases} \forall h \in \mathbf{H} \\ \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$SoC_{k,h+1}^b = SoC_{k,h}^b - \varphi_k^b \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{b,\star} \right\} \Delta_h, \quad \begin{cases} \forall h \in \mathbf{H} \\ \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbb{Z}_{km} \mathbb{I}_{km,h} = \mathbb{V}_{k,h} - \mathbb{V}_{m,h}, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall km \in \mathbf{L}\} \quad (5)$$

$$SoC_{k,h}^b = SoC_{k,i}^b, \quad \{\forall h = h_{\min}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N}\} \quad (6)$$

$$SoC_{k,h}^b = SoC_{k,f}^b, \quad \{\forall h = h_{\max}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N}\} \quad (7)$$

$$\left| \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^g \right| \leq S_{k,\text{nom}}^g, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N}\} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^g \right\} \geq 0, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N}\} \quad (9)$$

$$\left| \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{gd} \right| \leq S_{k,\text{nom}}^{gd}, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N}\} \quad (10)$$

$$\left| \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^b \right| \leq S_{k,\text{nom}}^b, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N}\} \quad (11)$$

$$0 \leq \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{dg} \right\} \leq S_{k,\text{nom}}^{dg} G_h^{dg}, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N}\} \quad (12)$$

$$P_{k,\min}^b \leq \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^b \right\} \leq P_{k,\max}^b, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N}\} \quad (13)$$

$$V_{\min} \leq |\mathbb{V}_{k,h}| \leq V_{\max}, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N}\} \quad (14)$$

$$\left| \mathbb{I}_{km,h} \right| \leq I_{km,\max}, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall km \in \mathbf{L}\} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{d,\star}$ represents the complex power consumption at node k in period h , $SoC_{k,h}^b$ and $SoC_{k,h+1}^b$ mean the state-of-charge in battery type- b connected at bus k in times h and $h + 1$, respectively; φ_k^b is known as the battery charge/discharge coefficient; $SoC_{k,i}^b$ and $SoC_{k,f}^b$ correspond to the initial and final state of charges expected for battery type- b connected at bus k ; \mathbb{Z}_{km} represents the impedance value associated with the branch that connects nodes k and m where the current flow $\mathbb{I}_{km,h}$ occurs in period h ; $S_{k,\text{nom}}^g$ and $S_{k,\text{nom}}^{dg}$ represents the maximum apparent power generation capabilities in the conventional and dispersed generation sources connected at bus k ; G_h^{dg} represents the daily availability generation curve associated with the dispersed source connected at bus k ; $S_{k,\text{nom}}^b$ represents the apparent power transference capacities of the power electronic converter interfacing the battery type- b connected at bus k , $P_{k,\min}^b$ and $P_{k,\max}^b$ mean the active power bounds applicable to the battery type- b connected at bus k , which permit active power absorption or injection; V_{\min} and V_{\max} correspond to the minimum and maximum voltage limits applicable to all nodes of the network at any period, and \mathbb{I}_{km}^{\max} is the maximum current transference capability associated with the conductor that connects nodes k and m . Note that \mathbf{L} represents the set containing all the network branches; in addition, h_{\min} and h_{\max} represent the initial and final elements in the set of periods \mathbf{H} .

Note that the interpretation of the set of constraints in (3)–(15) is the following: Equation (3) represents the power equilibrium at each node of the network and period of analysis [32]; Equation (4) is the energy storage capabilities applicable in batteries per period of analysis which is typically written using the state-of-charge concept [33]; Equation (6) defines the Ohm's law applied to each branch of the network which defines

the linear relation between voltages and currents in passive impedances. Equations (6) and (7) define the initial and final state of charges expected for batteries at the beginning and end of the operation timeline [13]. Inequality constraints (8) and (9) define the maximum power transference capabilities in the substation and constrain this conventional source to absorb active power, respectively. Inequality constraints (10) and (11) present the complex power transference bounds applicable to the DGs and batteries. Box-type constraint (12) ensures that the dispersed generators do not absorb active power and defines its power injection as a function of the renewable energy resource availability, and constraint (13) defines the lower and upper active power absorption/injection bounds applicable to the battery type- b connected at bus k in period h ; box-type constraint (14) ensures that the whole nodes of the network fulfill with the voltage regulation criterion imposed by the regulatory entities to distribution system operation in medium-voltage networks [34]; and inequality constraint (15) ensures that the current flow through each line in the route k and m nodes do not overpass the thermal bound on the conductor installed in this route.

Remark 3. *The set of constraints in (3)–(15) defines the technical operative constraints of an electrical network, including DERs. Most of these constraints are from the family of convex restrictions; however, the power balance constraint in (3) is non-convex due to the complex product among voltages, and box-type constraint (14) associated with the voltage regulation bound is non-convex due to the presence of the greater-or-equal condition in its left-hand-side part.*

Owing to the presence of the non-convex constraints (3) and (14), the complete optimization model (1)–(15) belongs from the family of non-convex optimization problems, for this reason, in this research as presented in next section, we will be interested in proposed a convexification of this optimization model via semidefinite programming (SDP) theory in the complex domain.

3. Semi-definite programming reformulation

SDP theory is a sub-field of the convex optimization theory that uses a counter-intuitive transformation of variables from \mathbb{R}^n to $\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ or is equivalent in the complex domain to solve some transformable optimization problems, such as the case of the optimal power flow problem in electrical networks [35, 36]. To apply the SDP theory to the EMS model defined from (1) to (15), the focus is concentrated on the power balance equilibrium defined by Equation (3) the product between voltage variables in the complex domain occurs. To do so, let us define a complex matrix as presented below.

$$\mathbb{X}_{n,n,h} = \mathbb{V}_{n,h}^{\star} \mathbb{V}_{n,h}^{\top}, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}\} \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbb{X}_{n,n,h} \in \text{Hermitian semidefinite}(n), \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}\} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Rank}(\mathbb{X}_{n,n,h}) = 1, \quad \{\forall h \in \mathbf{H}\} \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbb{X}_{n,n,h}$ represents a square matrix with dimensions $n \times n$ defining one for each time h , $\mathbb{V}_{n,h}$ is a complex vector

containing with dimensions $n \times 1$ associated with the voltage variables at each analysis period h . Operation $(\cdot)^\top$ represents the transpose operation without conjugating the elements inside the vector. Note that the hermitian semidefinite condition in the complex space $\mathbf{C}^{n \times n}$ is equivalent to the semidefinite condition in the set of real numbers, i.e., $\mathbf{R}^{n \times n}$.

The main complication with the new complex matrix $\mathbb{X}_{n,n,h}$ is that the rank imposition in Equation (18) is required to ensure that each vector $\mathbb{V}_{n,h}$ is completely recoverable from this matrix. However, this is a non-convex constraint that should be relaxed to obtain a convex equivalent reformulation of the EMS model (1)–(18) [35]. Note that if we consider that the rank constraint can be relaxed as recommended in [37], the power equilibrium constraint (3) can be rewritten as (19).

$$\mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{g,\star} + \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{dg,\star} + \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{b,\star} - \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{d,\star} = \sum_{m \in \mathbf{N}} \mathbb{Y}_{k,m} \mathbb{X}_{k,m,h}, \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \forall h \in \mathbf{H} \\ \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \end{array} \right\}, \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbb{X}_{k,m,h}$ represents the element (km) contained in the matrix $\mathbb{X}_{n,n,h}$ at period h

Observe that in the new solution space domain, i.e., the space of the semidefinite matrices, all the equations and constraints in the optimization model (1)–(15) that are defined as a function of the voltage variables $\mathbb{V}_{k,h}$ must be transformed using variables $\mathbb{X}_{k,k,h}$. To make this variable transformation, we begin with the objective function (1) associated with the expected grid energy losses during the timeline operation study case, defined as presented in Equation (20) (where was considered that).

$$\min E_{\text{loss}} = \text{Re} \left\{ \sum_{h \in \mathbf{H}} \sum_{k \in \mathbf{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathbf{N}} \mathbb{Y}_{k,m} \mathbb{X}_{k,m,h} \Delta_h \right\}. \quad (20)$$

Following this variable transformation, Ohm's law applied to each network branch in (5) is transformed using some algebraic manipulations, i.e., its multiplication by the conjugate functions in both sides, as presented below.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{Z}_{km} \mathbb{I}_{km,h} &= \mathbb{V}_{k,h} - \mathbb{V}_{m,h} \\ \mathbb{Z}_{km} \mathbb{I}_{km,h} \mathbb{Z}_{km}^* \mathbb{I}_{km,h}^* &= (\mathbb{V}_{k,h} - \mathbb{V}_{m,h}) (\mathbb{V}_{k,h} - \mathbb{V}_{m,h})^* \\ |\mathbb{Z}_{km}|^2 |\mathbb{I}_{km,h}|^2 &= \mathbb{V}_{k,h} \mathbb{V}_{k,h}^* - \mathbb{V}_{m,h} \mathbb{V}_{k,h}^* - \mathbb{V}_{k,h} \mathbb{V}_{m,h}^* + \mathbb{V}_{m,h} \mathbb{V}_{m,h}^* \end{aligned}$$

where it is possible to observe that $\mathbb{V}_{k,h} \mathbb{V}_{k,h}^*$ and $\mathbb{V}_{m,h} \mathbb{V}_{m,h}^*$ are equivalent to $\mathbb{X}_{k,k,h}$ and $\mathbb{X}_{m,m,h}$, in addition, $\mathbb{V}_{m,h} \mathbb{V}_{k,h}^*$ and $\mathbb{V}_{k,h} \mathbb{V}_{m,h}^*$ can be replaced by $\mathbb{X}_{m,k,h}$ and $\mathbb{X}_{k,m,h}$, respectively. An auxiliary variable $j_{km,h}$ is used to substitute the current variable $|\mathbb{I}_{km,h}|^2$. Considering all of these substitutions by taking the advantage that in Hermitian matrices $\mathbb{X}_{m,k,h} = \mathbb{X}_{k,m,h}^*$, the Ohm's law in (5) is transformed as defined in (21).

$$|\mathbb{Z}_{km}|^2 J_{km,h} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{X}_{k,k,h} + \mathbb{X}_{m,m,h}^- \\ \mathbb{X}_{m,k,h} - \mathbb{X}_{k,m,h} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \forall h \in \mathbf{H} \\ \forall km \in \mathbf{L} \end{array} \right\} \quad (21)$$

On the other hand, the voltage regulation bounds in (14) can be relaxed by neglecting the lower voltage bound as defined in (22).

$$|\mathbb{X}_{k,k,h}| \leq V_{\text{max}}^2, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (22)$$

in addition, with the new auxiliary available $J_{km,h}$, the thermal constraint in (15) can be rewritten as (23)

$$J_{km,h} \leq I_{km,\text{max}}^2, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall km \in \mathbf{L} \right\} \quad (23)$$

Remark 4. Note that the approximation in (22) is suitable for regular operation of distribution networks since the substation bus defines the voltage output in terminals of the substation as V_{nom} , which implies that it is expected that all the voltage nodes remain with voltage magnitudes near to this value.

For the sake of simplicity, the SDP approximation of the EMS model (1)–(15) for the efficient dispatch of DERs in distribution networks is presented again in the optimization model (24)–(39).

Objective functions

$$\min E_{\text{loss}} = \text{Re} \left\{ \sum_{h \in \mathbf{H}} \sum_{k \in \mathbf{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathbf{N}} \mathbb{Y}_{k,m} \mathbb{X}_{k,m,h} \Delta_h \right\}, \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \min E_{\text{cost}} = \text{Re} \left\{ \sum_{k \in \mathbf{N}} \sum_{h \in \mathbf{H}} (C_{\text{kWh},k}^g \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^g + C_{\text{AOM},k}^{dg} \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{dg}) \Delta_h \right\} \\ + \sum_{k \in \mathbf{N}} \sum_{h \in \mathbf{H}} C_{\text{kWh},k}^b \left| \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{b,\star} \right\} \right| \Delta_h. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Set of constraints

$$\mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{g,\star} + \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{dg,\star} + \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{b,\star} - \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{d,\star} = \sum_{m \in \mathbf{N}} \mathbb{Y}_{k,m} \mathbb{X}_{k,m,h}, \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \forall h \in \mathbf{H} \\ \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \end{array} \right\}, \quad (26)$$

$$SoC_{k,h+1}^b = SoC_{k,h}^b - \varphi_k^b \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{b,\star} \right\} \Delta_h, \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \forall h \in \mathbf{H} \\ \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \end{array} \right\} \quad (27)$$

$$|\mathbb{Z}_{km}|^2 J_{km,h} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{X}_{k,k,h} + \mathbb{X}_{m,m,h}^- \\ \mathbb{X}_{m,k,h} - \mathbb{X}_{k,m,h} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \forall h \in \mathbf{H} \\ \forall km \in \mathbf{L} \end{array} \right\}, \quad (28)$$

$$SoC_{k,h}^b = SoC_{k,i}^b, \quad \left\{ \forall h = h_{\text{min}}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (29)$$

$$SoC_{k,h}^b = SoC_{k,f}^b, \quad \left\{ \forall h = h_{\text{max}}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (30)$$

$$\left| \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^g \right| \leq S_{k,\text{nom}}^g, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (31)$$

$$\text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^g \right\} \geq 0, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (32)$$

$$\left| \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{gd} \right| \leq S_{k,\text{nom}}^{gd}, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (33)$$

$$\left| \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^b \right| \leq S_{k,\text{nom}}^b, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (34)$$

$$0 \leq \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^{dg} \right\} \leq S_{k,\text{nom}}^{dg} G_h^{dg}, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (35)$$

$$P_{k,\text{min}}^b \leq \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbb{S}_{k,h}^b \right\} \leq P_{k,\text{max}}^b, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (36)$$

$$|\mathbb{X}_{k,k,h}| \leq V_{\text{max}}^2, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall k \in \mathbf{N} \right\} \quad (37)$$

$$J_{km,h} \leq I_{km,\text{max}}^2, \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H}, \forall km \in \mathbf{L} \right\} \quad (38)$$

$$\mathbb{X}_{n,n,h} \in \text{Hermitian semidefinite}(n), \quad \left\{ \forall h \in \mathbf{H} \right\} \quad (39)$$

4. Test feeders' characterization

Two validate the application of the proposed SDP approach for designing an EMS to electrical networks with high penetration of DERs, two distribution networks with Colombian generation and demand characteristics are tested. The geographical location of these distribution networks is in Medellín and Capurganá, Colombia. These locations can be observed on the Colombian map presented in Fig. 1.

In the case of the Medellín adaptation of the distribution network, it corresponds to an urban grid powered by the national interconnected system of Colombia, while the rural distribution network in Capurganá is an isolated electrical network powered by diesel generators [13].

4.1. Urban distribution network in Medellín

An adaptation of the IEEE 33-bus grid with the demand and solar generation behavior in Medellín city, Colombia, was proposed to emulate the behavior of a typical urban distribution network in Colombia. The electrical configuration of this test feeder is depicted in Fig. 2. The main characteristic of this system is that it is fed with 12.66 kV in the terminals of the substation (phase-to-ground voltage).

The peak demand characterization of the IEEE 33-bus grid is presented in Table 1, where the information on the thermal limitations of the conductors is also reported, which has been taken from the 310-16 standard of the Colombian Technical Standard [13].

4.2. Rural distribution network in Capurganá

To emulate the electrical behavior of an isolated distribution network, the 27-bus grid proposed by authors of [38] was

Figure 1: Geographical location of Medellín and Capurganá in Colombia

Figure 2: Adaption of the IEEE 33-bus grid to emulate an urban network behavior

Table 1: Peak load consumption and branch parameters applied to the urban distribution grid

Line l	Node i	Node j	R_{ij} (Ω)	X_{ij} (Ω)	P_j (kW)	Q_j (kvar)	I_{ij}^{\max} (A)
1	1	2	0.0922	0.0477	100	60	385
2	2	3	0.4930	0.2511	90	40	355
3	3	4	0.3660	0.1864	120	80	240
4	4	5	0.3811	0.1941	60	30	240
5	5	6	0.8190	0.7070	60	20	240
6	6	7	0.1872	0.6188	200	100	110
7	7	8	1.7114	1.2351	200	100	85
8	8	9	1.0300	0.7400	60	20	70
9	9	10	1.0400	0.7400	60	20	70
10	10	11	0.1966	0.0650	45	30	55
11	11	12	0.3744	0.1238	60	35	55
12	12	13	1.4680	1.1550	60	35	55
13	13	14	0.5416	0.7129	120	80	40
14	14	15	0.5910	0.5260	60	10	25
15	15	16	0.7463	0.5450	60	20	20
16	16	17	1.2890	1.7210	60	20	20
17	17	18	0.7320	0.5740	90	40	20
18	2	19	0.1640	0.1565	90	40	40
19	19	20	1.5042	1.3554	90	40	25
20	20	21	0.4095	0.4784	90	40	20
21	21	22	0.7089	0.9373	90	40	20
22	3	23	0.4512	0.3083	90	50	85
23	23	24	0.8980	0.7091	420	200	85
24	24	25	0.8960	0.7011	420	200	40
25	6	26	0.2030	0.1034	60	25	125
26	26	27	0.2842	0.1447	60	25	110
27	27	28	1.0590	0.9337	60	20	110
28	28	29	0.8042	0.7006	120	70	110
29	29	30	0.5075	0.2585	200	600	95
30	30	31	0.9744	0.9630	150	70	55
31	31	32	0.3105	0.3619	210	100	30
32	32	33	0.3410	0.5302	60	40	20

adapted to the demand and solar generation conditions of the Capurganá municipality in Colombia. This distribution network is depicted in Fig. 3, operated in terminals of the substation with a nominal phase-to-ground voltage of about 23 kV.

The peak demand consumption and the branches characterization for the 27-bus grid are listed in Table 2.

4.3. Characterization of distributed energy resources

To emulate the daily behavior of the DERs connected in the urban and rural distribution grids, as depicted in Figs. 2 and 3, renewable generation based on photovoltaic (PV) sources and batteries based on Ion-Lithium characteristics are considered

Figure 3: Adaption of the 27-bus grid to emulate a rural network behavior

Table 2: Peak load consumption and branch parameters applied to the rural distribution grid

Line l	Node i	Node j	R_{ij} (Ω)	X_{ij} (Ω)	P_j (kW)	Q_j (kvar)	I_j^{\max} (A)
1	1	2	0.0140	0.6051	0	0	240
2	2	3	0.7463	1.0783	0	0	165
3	3	4	0.4052	0.5855	297.50	184.37	95
4	4	5	1.1524	1.6650	0	0	85
5	5	6	0.5261	0.7601	255.00	158.03	70
6	6	7	0.7127	1.0296	0	0	55
7	7	8	1.6628	2.4024	212.50	131.70	55
8	8	9	5.3434	3.1320	0	0	20
9	9	10	2.1522	1.2615	266.05	164.88	20
10	2	11	0.4052	0.5855	85.00	52.68	70
11	11	12	1.1524	1.6650	340	210.71	70
12	12	13	0.5261	0.7601	297.50	184.37	55
13	13	14	1.2358	1.1332	191.25	118.53	30
14	14	15	2.8835	2.6440	106.25	65.85	20
15	15	16	5.3434	3.1320	255.00	158.03	20
16	3	17	1.2942	1.1867	255.00	158.03	70
17	17	18	0.7027	0.6443	127.50	79.02	55
18	18	19	3.3234	1.9480	297.50	184.37	40
19	19	20	1.5172	0.8893	340	210.71	25
20	20	21	0.7127	1.0296	85.00	52.68	20
21	4	22	8.2528	2.9911	106.25	65.85	20
22	5	23	9.1961	3.3330	55.25	34.24	20
23	6	24	0.7463	1.0783	69.70	43.20	20
24	8	25	2.0112	0.7289	255.00	158.03	20
25	8	26	3.3234	1.9480	63.75	39.51	20
26	26	27	0.5261	0.7601	170	105.36	20

[13]. The location and sizes of the PV sources and batteries for both test feeders are described below.

- i. Three PV systems for the urban distribution network are located at nodes 13, 25, and 30. These generators' nominal power generation capabilities are 1125, 1320, and 999 kW, respectively. In the case of batteries, these are located at nodes 6 (type C), 14 (type A), and 31 (type B).
- ii. Three PV systems for the rural distribution network are located at nodes 5, 9, and 19. These generators' nominal power generation capabilities are 1012.5, 1188, and 899.1 kW, respectively. In addition, three batteries located at node 3 (type C), node 8 (type A), and node 19 (type B) are employed.
- iii. The voltage regulation bound in both test feeders is set between -10% and +10% of the substation voltage output.

Note that the batteries mentioned above are characterized in Fig. 3. In addition, to ensure the efficient operation of the batteries, the minimum and maximum state of charges are set between 10% and 90%.

Table 3: Batteries' characterization

Type	Capacity (kWh)	Charge time (h)	Discharge time (h)
A	1000	4	4
B	1500	4	4
C	2000	5	5

Fig. 4 depicts the daily demand behavior and renewable generation availability for the urban and rural areas considered in this study. It is worth mentioning that this information was obtained from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration database between January 1st and December 31st, 2019 [13].

Figure 4: Daily renewable generation availability and demand consumption for urban and rural grids.

On the other hand, the characterization of the objective functions in both distribution grids is listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Objective function coefficients (These data must be corrected)

Parameter	Urban (USD/kWh)	Rural (USD/kWh)
$C_{kWh,k}^g$	0.1302	0.2913
$C_{AOM,k}^b$	0.2913	0.2913
$C_{AOM,k}^{dis}$	0.0019	0.0019

Note that in the case of the urban distribution network, a variable energy purchasing costs scenario in substation terminals is considered. Fig. 5 depicts the daily expected energy purchasing cost variation [29]; however, this variation does not apply to the rural distribution grid since, for a daily

operation scenario, the energy purchasing costs of the diesel have a fixed value.

Figure 5: Expected daily generation costs applicable to the urban grid.

5. Computational validation

For this computational implementation, the MATLAB programming environment, version 2022b, was used on a PC with an AMD Ryzen 7 3700 2.3 GHz processor and 16.0 GB RAM running on a 64-bit version of Microsoft Windows 10 Single Language. The solution of the proposed SDP model is reached using the CVX optimization environment by using the SDPT3 and SEDUMI solvers [39, 40].

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed SDP model in dealing with the efficient daily operation of DERs in medium-voltage distribution networks, a complete comparative analysis considering unity power factor in BESS and DGs is made by using [13] as reference. This work used three metaheuristic optimization algorithms for numerical validations in the 27- and IEEE 33-bus grids. These algorithms correspond to the continuous genetic algorithm (CGA), the parallel particle swarm optimizer (PPSO), and the parallel vortex search algorithm (PVSA).

5.1. Comparative analysis

A comparative analysis with the literature report in [13] is made considering that all the distributed energy resources work with unity power factor, i.e., no reactive power injection capabilities are considered. Table 5 presents the numerical solutions for the urban and rural networks. Note that the benchmark case corresponds to the daily operation of the distribution networks by assuming that all the batteries are disconnected.

Numerical results in Table 5 show that:

- i. For both tested scenarios, including energy loss minimization or energy production cost reduction, the proposed convex model based on the SDP approximation presents better minimum solutions, i.e., solutions closeness to the global optimum. In contrast, the best metaheuristic optimizer, i.e., the PVSA, is stuck in local optimal solutions.

Table 5: Comparative analysis considering unity power factor operation in the urban and rural distribution networks

Method	E_{cost} (USD/day)	E_{loss} (kWh/day)
Urban Distribution network		
Benchmark case	6999.05300	2484.57466
CGA	6927.84650	2431.47454
PPSO	6905.22318	2380.83359
PVSA	6900.19331	2377.80281
SDP	6897.69280	2373.40533
Rural Distribution network		
Benchmark case	15424.0300	582.3771
CGA	15424.0300	560.7334
PPSO	15421.6568	541.0004
PVSA	15421.4092	539.1604
SDP	15420.3889	538.8178

- ii. Concerning the benchmark cases, the SDP approach in the urban network showed an improvement of about USD/day 101.3602, i.e., 1.4481% when the daily operating costs are analyzed, while for the rural distribution network, this index is improved about USD/day 3.6411, i.e., 0.0236%.
- iii. When the objective function regarding energy losses is analyzed, the urban distribution network improves about 111.1693kWh/day, i.e., 4.4744%, while for the urban distribution network, this improvement was about 43.5593 kWh/day, i.e., 7.4796%.

In addition, when the SDP approach is numerical compared to the best metaheuristic optimizer reported in the specialized literature, i.e., the PVSA approach, in the case of energy minimization cost, the SDP permits improvements of about USD/day 2.5005 and 1.0203, in the urban and rural networks, respectively. Regarding the daily energy loss coefficient, the graduation in the urban and rural networks, concerning the PVSA approach, were kWh/day 4.3974 and 0.3426, respectively.

Remark 5. The most important key in the comparative analysis between the PVSA and the proposed SDP approach does not lie in the small reductions in favor of the convex approach but in the effectiveness of the SDP method since their solution are 100% reliable (i.e., repeatable), with negligible standard deviations, i.e., 1×10^{-16} , while the metaheuristic PVSA approach due to its randomness nature does not offer 100% of repeatability and at each evaluation, a different solution can be found.

5.2. Numerical analysis considering variable power factor

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed SDP relaxation to operate DERs in medium-voltage distribution networks considering variable power factor operation, the following simulation scenarios are tested:

- i. S_1 The PV sources are daily dispatched considering unity power factor and batteries operating with variable power factors.

- ii. S_2 The PV sources are daily dispatched considering variable power factor and batteries operating with a unity power factor.
- iii. S_3 All DERs work with variable power factor.

For comparative purposes, the benchmark case corresponds to the numerical results reported in Table 6 where the PVs and BESS systems are dispatched with unitary power factors, i.e., the SDP results renamed as S_0 .

Table 6: Comparative analysis considering unity power factor operation in the urban and rural distribution networks

Method	E_{cost} (USD/day)	E_{loss} (kWh/day)
Urban Distribution network		
S_0	6897.69280	2373.40533
S_1	6798.51070	1470.36936
S_2	6769.86169	1297.26390
S_3	6766.98979	1266.72210
Rural Distribution network		
S_0	15420.3889	538.8178
S_1	15386.5571	418.5530
S_2	15380.8157	395.8794
S_3	15376.6112	385.9069

Results in Table 6 show that:

- i. Using variable reactive power compensation on each DERs during the day allows for significant reductions in daily energy operating costs and daily energy loss values. In the case of the urban (rural) distribution network, adding reactive power capabilities to batteries in S_1 resulted in reductions of approximately 1.4379% (0.2193%) and 38.0481% (22.3201%) in energy production and operating costs, as well as the daily energy loss value, respectively, compared to the scenario with unity power factor operation, i.e., S_0 . However, both indicators achieve additional gains when photovoltaic sources are operated with variable power factor in S_2 , resulting in reductions of approximately 1.8532% (0.2566%) and 45.3417% (26.5282%), respectively. When comparing S_2 and S_1 , the use of variable power factor in PVs is more effective than using variable power factor only in BESS. This can be explained by the fact that the nominal sizes of the PVs are more than two times larger than the sizes of the BESS. When both DERs are operated with variable power factor, the most significant reductions in both optimization indexes are found, corresponding to 1.8949% (0.2839%) and 46.6285% (28.3790%), respectively.
- ii. The main finding regarding variable power factor DERs is that the objective function related to energy purchasing and operating costs, denoted as E_{costs} , shows improvements in all simulated scenarios (S_1 to S_3) compared to S_0 . This situation is understandable because reactive power injected by DERs locally reduces reactive power flows from conventional substations to loads. As a result, the grid has reduced energy losses, meaning

less active power is needed to meet all the loads. This ultimately leads to additional reductions in the economic objective function.

5.3. Complementary analysis

To observe the positive effect of considering variable power factor operation in DERs. Fig. 6 presents the energy production in terminals of the substation in S_0 and S_3 in both test feeders, when E_{costs} is minimized.

Figure 6: Daily energy production behavior in terminals of the conventional source: (a) urban distribution network, and (b) rural distribution network

Observe that the main result in Fig. 6(a) is that the availability of renewable power in the PV sources (see Fig. 4) shows that even if energy demand is more significant than 60% along the day (for urban grid), the energy production in the conventional substation is drastically reduced when renewable energy is injected from 6 to 19 hours (equivalent to a net profit of about USD/day 130.70301). Note that similar behavior can be observed in energy generation in terminals of the diesel source (see Fig. 4(b)); however, due to the small sizes of the PV plants, the reduction effect is not highly appreciable, nevertheless, economically speaking the daily reductions in the rural operation scenario when compared S_0 and S_3 was about USD/day 43.7777.

Finally, Fig. 7 depicts the daily energy loss behavior in both test feeders when compared S_0 and S_3 .

Results in Fig. 7 confirm the effectiveness of considering variable power factor operation in DERs when energy losses is

Figure 7: Daily energy losses behavior: (a) urban distribution network, and (b) rural distribution network

minimized since the availability of reactive power injection in BESS and PVs is defined by the usage of the apparent power capabilities of the converting interfacing DERs, which implies, that for example in the case of PVs (see Fig.4), all the periods where PV is not dispatched in their maximum capability, it is possible to manage reactive power, this includes night period. For this reason, it is observed in Figs. 7(a) and 7(b) that energy losses are always lower in the variable power factor in S_3 when compared with unitary power factor operation in S_0 .

6. Conclusions and future works

The problem of efficiently designing an EMS for DERs in medium voltage distribution networks was addressed in this research. The proposed approach involved using a SDP approximation in the complex domain, utilizing Hermitian semidefinite matrices to represent the exact nonlinear non-convex model of the EMS. Numerical simulations were conducted on two medium voltage distribution networks consisting of 27 and 33 nodes, using the actual operational characteristics of two electrical networks in Colombia (specifically, the Capurganá and Medellín municipalities). These simulations demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed SDP model when compared to metaheuristic optimizers.

A comparative analysis between the SDP approach and the PVSA methodology, considering unity power factor operation, demonstrated that the convex optimization model allowed for discovering better objective function values than metaheuristics. This finding confirmed the local nature properties of metaheuristics optimization algorithms. In addition, the advantage of the SDP approach is its reliability, which is 100% with extra-low standard deviations, i.e., with any metaheuristic approach due to its random-based nature.

Numerical simulations considering variable power factors in BESS and PVs demonstrated that concerning the unity power factor operation, important gains regarding economic or technical objective functions were obtained in both test feeders. These results confirmed that reactive power injection permits improvements in voltage profile, which reduces the energy loss value on the day of operation. This reduction is directly connected with the reductions in the total energy purchasing costs in terminals of the substation since the energy required for supplying energy losses is reduced, generating a positive profit for the distribution company.

In future works, the following developments can be made: (i) to reformulate the problem of DERs' operation using conic optimization models that allow for the optimal allocation of BESS and/or PVs, (ii) to extend the proposed formulation for possible uncertainties in demand profiles and renewable generation curves considering robust or stochastic convex optimization techniques, and (iii) to integrate the efficient operation problem in distribution networks with the planning stages, i.e., the optimal selection of the optimal feeder route and the assignment of the conductor sizes.

CRediT author statement

V. M. Garrido-Árevalo: conceptualization, methodology, software, validation, formal analysis, investigation, resources, data curation, writing (original draft, review, and editing), visualization. **O.D. Montoya:** conceptualization, methodology, software, validation, formal analysis, investigation, resources, data curation, writing (original draft, review, and editing), visualization. **W. Gil-González:** conceptualization, methodology, writing (review and editing), supervision, project administration, acquisition of funds. **L. F. Grisales-Noreña:** conceptualization, methodology, writing (review and editing). **J. C. Hernández:** supervision, project administration, acquisition of funds.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could appear to have influenced the work reported in this paper.

References

- [1] E. E. Michaelides, Decarbonization of the electricity generation sector and its effects on sustainability goals, *Sustainable Energy Research* 10 (1) (Aug. 2023). doi:10.1186/s40807-023-00080-1.

- [2] A. Jain, S. Yamujala, A. Gaur, P. Das, R. Bhakar, J. Mathur, Power sector decarbonization planning considering renewable resource variability and system operational constraints, *Applied Energy* 331 (2023) 120404. doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.120404.
- [3] W. Strielkowski, L. Civiń, E. Tarkhanova, M. Tvaronavičienė, Y. Petrenko, Renewable Energy in the Sustainable Development of Electrical Power Sector: A Review, *Energies* 14 (24) (2021) 8240. doi: 10.3390/en14248240.
- [4] A. Qazi, F. Hussain, N. A. Rahim, G. Hardaker, D. Alghazzawi, K. Shaban, K. Haruna, Towards sustainable energy: A systematic review of renewable energy sources, technologies, and public opinions, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 63837–63851. doi:10.1109/access.2019.2906402.
- [5] S. Junlakarn, R. Diewvilai, K. Audomvongseree, Stochastic modeling of renewable energy sources for capacity credit evaluation, *Energies* 15 (14) (2022) 5103. doi:10.3390/en15145103.
- [6] P. Hajiamoosha, A. Rastgou, S. Bahramara, S. M. Bagher Sadati, Stochastic energy management in a renewable energy-based microgrid considering demand response program, *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 129 (2021) 106791. doi:10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.106791.
- [7] A. Valencia, R. A. Hincapie, R. A. Gallego, Optimal location, selection, and operation of battery energy storage systems and renewable distributed generation in medium–low voltage distribution networks, *Journal of Energy Storage* 34 (2021) 102158. doi:10.1016/j.est.2020.102158.
- [8] L. F. Grisales-Noreña, O. D. Montoya, J. C. Hernández, An Efficient EMS for BESS in Monopolar DC Networks with High Penetration of Renewable Generation: A Convex Approximation, *Batteries* 9 (2) (2023) 84. doi:10.3390/batteries9020084.
- [9] R. A. Hincapie I., R. A. Gallego R., J. R. Mantovani, A decomposition approach for integrated planning of primary and secondary distribution networks considering distributed generation, *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 106 (2019) 146–157. doi:10.1016/j.ijepes.2018.09.040.
- [10] M. Delfanti, D. Falabretti, M. Merlo, Dispersed generation impact on distribution network losses, *Electric Power Systems Research* 97 (2013) 10–18. doi:10.1016/j.epsr.2012.11.018.
- [11] S. Lakshmi, S. Ganguly, Transition of Power Distribution System Planning from Passive to Active Networks: A State-of-the-Art Review and a New Proposal, Springer Singapore, 2017, pp. 87–117. doi: 10.1007/978-981-10-7188-1_4.
- [12] M. S. Alam, S. A. Arefifar, Energy management in power distribution systems: Review, classification, limitations and challenges, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 92979–93001. doi:10.1109/access.2019.2927303.
- [13] L. Grisales-Noreña, B. Cortés-Caicedo, O. D. Montoya, J. Hernández, G. Alcalá, A battery energy management system to improve the financial, technical, and environmental indicators of colombian urban and rural networks, *Journal of Energy Storage* 65 (2023) 107199. doi:10.1016/j.est.2023.107199.
- [14] V. Suresh, P. Janik, M. Jasinski, J. M. Guerrero, Z. Leonowicz, Microgrid energy management using metaheuristic optimization algorithms, *Applied Soft Computing* 134 (2023) 109981. doi:10.1016/j.asoc.2022.109981.
- [15] W. J. Gutjahr, *Convergence Analysis of Metaheuristics*, Springer US, 2009, pp. 159–187. doi:10.1007/978-1-4419-1306-7_6.
- [16] L. F. Grisales-Noreña, O. D. Montoya, B. Cortés-Caicedo, F. Zishan, J. Rosero-García, Optimal Power Dispatch of PV Generators in AC Distribution Networks by Considering Solar, Environmental, and Power Demand Conditions from Colombia, *Mathematics* 11 (2) (2023) 484. doi:10.3390/math11020484.
- [17] C. D. Iweh, S. Gyamfi, E. Tanyi, E. Effah-Donyina, Distributed generation and renewable energy integration into the grid: Prerequisites, push factors, practical options, issues and merits, *Energies* 14 (17) (2021) 5375.
- [18] P. Teimourzadeh Baboli, M. Shahparasti, M. Parsa Moghaddam, M. R. Haghifam, M. Mohamadian, Energy management and operation modelling of hybrid ac–dc microgrid, *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution* 8 (10) (2014) 1700–1711.
- [19] S. Helal, R. Najee, M. O. Hanna, M. F. Shaaban, A. Osman, M. S. Hassan, An energy management system for hybrid microgrids in remote communities, in: 2017 IEEE 30th Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering (CCECE), IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–4.
- [20] R. Khalilpour, A. Vassallo, Planning and operation scheduling of PV-battery systems: A novel methodology, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 53 (2016) 194–208.
- [21] M. Kraning, Y. Wang, E. Akuiyibo, S. Boyd, Operation and configuration of a storage portfolio via convex optimization, *IFAC Proceedings volumes* 44 (1) (2011) 10487–10492.
- [22] W. Gil-González, O. D. Montoya, L. F. Grisales-Noreña, A. Escobar-Mejía, Optimal economic–environmental operation of bess in ac distribution systems: A convex multi-objective formulation, *Computation* 9 (12) (2021) 137.
- [23] R. Zafar, J. Ravishankar, J. E. Fletcher, H. R. Pota, Optimal dispatch of battery energy storage system using convex relaxations in unbalanced distribution grids, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 16 (1) (2019) 97–108.
- [24] F. Molina-Martin, O. D. Montoya, L. F. Grisales-Noreña, J. C. Hernández, C. A. Ramírez-Vanegas, Simultaneous minimization of energy losses and greenhouse gas emissions in AC distribution networks using BESS, *Electronics* 10 (9) (2021) 1002.
- [25] V. Jani, H. Abdi, Optimal allocation of energy storage systems considering wind power uncertainty, *Journal of Energy Storage* 20 (2018) 244–253.
- [26] O. Ivanov, B.-C. Neagu, G. Grigoras, F. Scarlatache, M. Gavrilas, A metaheuristic algorithm for flexible energy storage management in residential electricity distribution grids, *Mathematics* 9 (19) (2021) 2375.
- [27] L. Grisales-Noreña, O. D. Montoya, W. Gil-Gonzalez, Integration of energy storage systems in AC distribution networks: Optimal location, selecting, and operation approach based on genetic algorithms, *Journal of Energy Storage* 25 (2019) 100891.
- [28] S. Sharma, K. Niazi, K. Verma, T. Rawat, Coordination of different DGs, BESS and demand response for multi-objective optimization of distribution network with special reference to Indian power sector, *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 121 (2020) 106074.
- [29] L. Grisales-Noreña, O. D. Montoya, C. A. Ramos-Paja, An energy management system for optimal operation of BSS in DC distributed generation environments based on a parallel PSO algorithm, *Journal of Energy Storage* 29 (2020) 101488. doi:10.1016/j.est.2020.101488.
- [30] A. R. Aldik, B. Venkatesh, Fast SDP Relaxation of the Optimal Power Flow Using the Line-Wise Model for Representing Meshed Transmission Networks, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* (2022) 1–15doi:10.1109/tpwrs.2022.3200970.
- [31] S. M. Stefanov, Numerical solution of systems of nonlinear equations defined by convex functions, *Journal of Interdisciplinary Mathematics* 25 (4) (2021) 951–962. doi:10.1080/09720502.2021.1917061.
- [32] N. Mithulananthan, M. M. A. Salama, C. A. Cañizares, J. Reeve, Distribution System Voltage Regulation and Var Compensation for Different Static Load Models, *The International Journal of Electrical Engineering & Education* 37 (4) (2000) 384–395. doi:10.7227/ijeee.37.4.8.
- [33] A. Anvari-Moghaddam, J. Dulout, C. Alonso, B. Jammes, J. M. Guerrero, Optimal Design and Operation Management of Battery-Based Energy Storage Systems (BESS) in Microgrids, in: X. Chen, W. Cao (Eds.), *Advancements in Energy Storage Technologies*, IntechOpen, Rijeka, 2017, Ch. 7. doi:10.5772/intechopen.71640. URL <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.71640>
- [34] V. Ilea, C. Bovo, D. Falabretti, M. Merlo, C. Arrigoni, R. Bonera, M. Rodolfi, Voltage Control Methodologies in Active Distribution Networks, *Energies* 13 (12) (2020) 3293. doi:10.3390/en13123293.
- [35] X. Bai, H. Wei, K. Fujisawa, Y. Wang, Semidefinite programming for optimal power flow problems, *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 30 (6–7) (2008) 383–392. doi:10.1016/j.ijepes.2007.12.003.
- [36] B. D. Biswas, S. Kamalasadán, Alternative SDP Relaxed Optimal Power Flow Formulation for Radial Distribution Networks, in: 2022 IEEE International Conference on Power Electronics, Smart Grid, and Renewable Energy (PESGRE), IEEE, 2022. doi:10.1109/pesgre52268.2022.9715879.
- [37] H. Mahboubi, J. Lavaei, Analysis of Semidefinite Programming

Relaxation of Optimal Power Flow for Cyclic Networks, in: 2018 IEEE Conference on Decision and Control (CDC), IEEE, 2018. doi:10.1109/cdc.2018.8618935.

- [38] H. Falaghi, M. Ramezani, M.-R. Haghifam, K. Milani, Optimal selection of conductors in radial distribution systems with time varying load, in: 18th International Conference and Exhibition on Electricity Distribution (CIRED 2005), IEE, 2005. doi:10.1049/cp:20051351.
- [39] M. Grant, S. Boyd, CVX: Matlab software for disciplined convex programming, version 2.1, <http://cvxr.com/cvx> (Mar. 2014).
- [40] M. Grant, S. Boyd, Graph implementations for nonsmooth convex programs, in: V. Blondel, S. Boyd, H. Kimura (Eds.), Recent Advances in Learning and Control, Lecture Notes in Control and Information Sciences, Springer-Verlag Limited, 2008, pp. 95–110, http://stanford.edu/~boyd/graph_dcp.html.